

HISPANIC REVIEW

UNIVERSITY of PENNSYLVANIA

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Professor María Dolores Dobón
Mary Baldwin College
Staunton, VA 24401-9983

Dear Professor Dobón:

We have received a review copy of the following book:

Azorín. *Saavedra Fajardo*. Ed. by Francisco Javier Díez de Revenga. Berkeley: California UP, 1994. 212 pp.

Azorín. *Judit*. Ed. by Mariano de Paco y Antonio Díez Mediavilla. Alicante: Caja de Ahorros del Mediterráneo, 1993. 252 pages.

We have fixed a 1,250 word limit for the review of this book, and we would appreciate it very much if you would consent to do the review for us.

Reviewers are asked to submit their review manuscripts no later than six months after the date on which they receive their review copies. Upon completion of your review, the book would of course become your property.

If, as we hope, you accept our invitation, we shall send you complete instructions for the preparation of your review, together with the review copy.

Sincerely yours,

Ignacio Javier López